

Nurses Job Satisfaction Analysis

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ABSTRACT

The present study has been divided in to five parts. In the “Objective” Section the problem is set to be explored, and its importance to the field of Nursing in which the research belongs. An effort has been made to present a detailed discourse on the points and prove the points. In “Literature Review” Section the sources of this project has been cited. Data is collected with the help of questionnaire. This type of questionnaire is closed ended. Information related to different hospitals and different Nurses. In the “data analysis” Section a detailed and graphical representation of data has been given. Along with graphs, percentage of choice has also been given and the detailed overview of the data is also written there. In the “Finding” Section remedy of the problems has been suggested and according to the needs and recommendations. The details are given in the form of percentage and explanation is also given with it. In “Appendix” detailed overview of the arguments by the staff Nurses are presented in a table view and questionnaire is given in appendix section B. This questionnaire given is being filled by the different nurses.

Keywords: Nurses; Job; Satisfaction; Job Satisfaction; Analysis.

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INTRODUCTION

Although nurse job satisfaction has been linked to retention, a gap remains in identifying specific factors which can be managed or changed to improve satisfaction. Knowing that nurse satisfaction is related to physician interactions, policies, or autonomy provides very broad areas of interest with few specific actions that can to immediate improvement.

Policies are generally applicable to all without making any distinction for generational preferences or needs. Benefits are one of the few variables which can be adjusted for each generation or even each person. A generational analysis of staff nurses in relation to their happiness with their financial and non-financial benefits is presented.

Benefits as incentives are related to job satisfaction, perceived stress, and intent to stay on their current jobs. The purpose of the Nurse Incentives is to determine satisfaction with current employment and incentives make a nurse standing on job and potential managerial actions.

Objective

1. The basic idea behind the study is find out problem faced by the Nurses during duties.
2. On the basis of the analyses and a solid and perfect solution is to be proved for the eradication of problems especially on the end of the Nurses.
3. The project will be a use full tool in solving those problems faced by the Nurses and also by some of the Nurses especially while nursing duties are different level like clinical Nurse, Nursing, Instructor, Chief Nursing superintendent, Nurse Manager.

Research Question

What do you think are the problems faced by Pakistani Staff Nurses paper research questionnaire about twenty questions? The question should be relevant to the topic through which you can highlight the problems of job satisfaction in Nursing. Select the Nurses who have been working for several levels at hospital as nurse.

I had distributed the questionnaire to them. On the base of feedback given by the nurses prepare a brief report statistically and submit it to the tutor for analyzing master process.

Manuscript Layout

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LITERATURE REVIEW

Job Satisfaction may be viewed as the pleasurable emotional state resulting from the perception of the known as Job as fulfilling the important job values.

The current nursing shortage and high turnover is of great concern in many countries because of its impact upon the efficiency and effectiveness of any health-care delivery system. Recruitment and retention of nurses and persistent problems associated with job satisfaction. This paper analyses the growing literature relating to job satisfaction among nurses and concludes that more research is required to understand the relative importance of the many identified factors to job satisfaction. It is argued that the absence of a robust causal model incorporating organizational, professional and personal variables is undermining the development of interventions to improve Nurse Job.

Once involved in the process, employee’s productivity can be further increased by measuring both individual and team performance against several objectives on a regular basis. Objectives are the day-

to-day tasks that must be accomplished in order to achieve the company's goals. Many objectives are stated as ratios, thus establishing tough but achievable numerical targets.

Although some employees are given the opportunity to win awards for job accomplishments, if managers formally recognize their abilities and contributions in the presence of their peers, it can mean more to them than any awards or trophies. Unfortunately, not enough companies are aware of the value and significance of employee recognition. For something that costs very little and can be as simple as a "thank you" for doing an excellent job, the payback is much more than seems possible. Even acknowledging the efforts made by employees to reach an objective can result in a more motivated and productive work team.

METHODOLOGY

This project is questionnaire based and Nurse oriented, therefore data is collected with the help of questionnaire the type of questionnaire is close ended.

Some of the questions are based on only strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed, strongly disagreed options and some of the questions for the purpose of information collection 50 candidates have been selected from different hospitals following hospital's visited for this purpose.

1. Allied Hospital Faisalabad
2. Faisal Abad Institute of Cardiology
3. Aziz Fatima Hospital Faisalabad
4. Mian Muhammad Trust Hospital Faisalabad
5. District Head Quarter Hospital Faisalabad
6. Government General Hospital Faisalabad
7. Mayo Hospital Lahore
8. Ganga Ram Hospital Lahore

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Table 1: Q.1: Job satisfaction of Nurses increases quality care of patient

Sr. No	Nurses	Frequency	Percentage
1	Strongly Agree	35	70
2	Agree	12	24
3	Disagree	2	4
4	Strongly Disagree	1	2
5	Total	50	100

Explanation

Thirty-Five Nurses out of fifty strongly agree to that job Satisfaction through direct Method. Whereas, only twelve nurses are agreeing two disagree and one strongly disagree.

DATA ANALYSIS

Table 2: Q.2: Job Satisfaction improves performance of nurses

Sr. No	Nurses	Frequency	Percentage
1	Strongly Agree	24	48
2	Agree	16	32
3	Disagree	4	8
4	Strongly Disagree	6	12
5	Total	50	100

Explanation

Twenty-four nurses out of fifty strongly agree to that job satisfaction through direct method. Whereas only sixteen nurses are agreeing four disagrees and six strongly disagree level of nurses.

Table 3: Q3: Stress increase relationship can cause negative Effective on job satisfaction

Sr. No	Nurses	Frequency	Percentage
1	Strongly Agree	30	60
2	Agree	20	40
3	Disagree	Nil	Nil
4	Strongly Disagree	Nil	Nil
5	Total	50	100

Explanation

Thirty Nurses out of fifty strongly agree to it that job satisfaction through direct Method. Whereas, only twenty Nurses are agreeing and no disagree and strongly agree. Level of nurses.

Table 4: Q.4: Reward from management may increase job satisfaction.

Sr. No	Nurses	Frequency	Percentage
1	Strongly Agree	36	72
2	Agree	12	24
3	Disagree	1	2
4	Strongly Disagree	1	2
5	Total	50	100

Explanation

Thirty-six Nurses out of fifty strongly agreed to that job satisfaction through direct method. Whereas, only twelve nurses are agreeing on nurse disagreed and one strongly disagreed.

Table 5: Q.5: High paid nurses perform better

Sr. No	Nurses	Frequency	Percentage
1	Strongly Agree	33	66
2	Agree	13	26
3	Disagree	2	4
4	Strongly Disagree	2	4
5	Total	50	100

Explanation

Thirty-three Nurses out of strongly agree to it that job satisfaction through direct method. Whereas, only thirteen Nurses are agreeing two disagree and two strongly disagree level of nurses.

Fact Finding of the Analysis

1. In question # 1 70% of the Nurses are in the favour through direct method of nursing job satisfaction, while 24% are confirmed for doing job in Nursing, 4 and 2% are not intended to continue with this job.
2. In question # 2 48% of the Nurses are in the favour, while 32% are confirmed for doing job in Nursing, 20% disagreed and not intended to continue with this job.
3. In question # 3 60% of the Nurses are in the favour, while 40% are confirmed for doing job in Nursing, and no one disagreed or strongly disagreed on this statement.
4. In question # 4 72% of the Nurses are in the favour, while 40% are confirmed for doing job in Nursing, and no one disagreed or strongly disagreed on this statement.
5. In question # 5 66% of the Nurses are in the favour, while 24% are confirmed for doing job in Nursing, totally 4% are not intended to continue with this job.
6. In question # 6 46% of the Nurses are in the favour, while 32% are confirmed for doing this job in Nursing, 22% are not intended to continue with this job.
7. In question # 7 52% of the Nurses are in the favour, while 46% are confirmed for doing job in Nursing, and 2% are not intended to continue with this job.
8. In question # 8 64% of the Nurses are in the favour, while 32% are confirmed for doing job in Nursing, 16% are not intended to continue with this job.
9. In question # 9 38% of the Nurses are in the favour, while 26% are confirmed for doing job in Nursing, 36% are not intended to continue with this job.
10. In question # 10 48% of the Nurses are in the favour, while 44% are confirmed for doing job in Nursing, and 8% are not intended to continue with this job.
11. In question # 11 64% of the Nurses are in the favour, while 34% are confirmed for doing job in Nursing, and 2% are not intended to continue with this job.
12. In question # 12 74% of the Nurses are in the favour, while 26% are confirmed for doing job in Nursing, and no one disagreed or strongly disagreed on this statement.
13. In question # 13 74% of the Nurses are in the favour, while 26% are confirmed for doing job in Nursing, and no one disagreed or strongly disagreed on this statement.
14. In question # 14 62% of the Nurses are in the favour, while 38% are confirmed for doing job in Nursing, and no one disagreed or strongly disagreed on this statement.
15. In question # 15 64% of the Nurses are in the favour, while 36% are confirmed for doing job in Nursing, and no one disagreed or strongly disagreed on this statement.
16. In question # 16 72% of the Nurses are in the favour, while 28% are confirmed for doing job in Nursing, and no one disagreed or strongly disagreed on this statement.
17. In question # 17 64% of the Nurses are in the favour, while 32% are confirmed for doing job in Nursing, and 4% are not intended to continue with this job.
18. In question # 18 50% of the Nurses are in the favour, while 46% are confirmed for doing job in Nursing, and 4% are not intended to continue with this job.
19. In question # 19 64% of the Nurses are in the favour, while 32% are confirmed for doing job in Nursing, and 4% are not intended to continue with this job.
20. In question # 20 52% of the Nurses are in the favour, while 40% are confirmed for doing job in Nursing, and 8% are not intended to continue with this job.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

I'm delighted at this stage when I had gathered all the information and collection of important data about "Job Satisfaction in Nursing" and the problem facing area of this particular job.

I finally came to know through my data analysis and important information that "Nursing" is not an easy task about which a nurse or an ordinary woman or girl when choose this profession there are too many problems and loop holes which might have to be clear for the evolution and the betterment of the "Job Satisfaction in Nursing".

The job is a dignity in itself and raise the moral of an ordinary girl when she is standing in the days of stress, causalities and in emergency by paying off her time with diligence and honestly for the sake of humanity and for the sake of "Motherland".

I must say Nursing is not an easy job but who accepts it I "SALUTE" them all.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Management Initiatives
2. Creativity & Innovations
3. Quality Improvement Process
4. Mentoring and Coaching
5. Cultural Sensitivity
6. Management Theory of Establishing of quality exchange with nurse employees
7. Process to provide smooth transitions for nurse graduate and academic setting to a Professional setting.

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ANNEXTURE

Questionnaire for Nurses job satisfaction

Research Topic for Nurses job satisfaction

Respected Staff Nurses

We are going to conduct research on topic job satisfaction. Your valuable response will be great asset for the completion of this project and assure you that your personal information will not be disclosed. Thank you in advance for your cooperation. Please follow the given key to show your response. Respected staff Nurses Please shows your valuable response by uses following keys.

Name _____
Gender _____
Course Program _____
Qualification _____

- A. Strongly Agree
- B. Agree
- C. Disagree
- D. Strongly Disagree

Project Job Satisfaction Nurses

Sr. #	Statements	A	B	C	D
1-	Job satisfaction of Nurses increases quality care of patient.				
2-	Job satisfaction improves performance of nurses.				
3-	Stress increase relationship can cause negative effect on the job satisfaction.				
4-	Reward from management may increase job satisfaction.				
5-	High paid nurses perform better.				
6-	Low paid nurse cannot perform well.				
7-	Job satisfaction enhances the organizational achievement.				
8-	I am satisfied with my duty hours.				
9-	I am satisfied my duty roster policy.				
10-	Job dissatisfaction creates family problems.				
11-	Sufficient staff is the reason of job satisfaction.				
12-	Job satisfaction increases efficiency.				
13-	Good management can increase job satisfaction.				
14-	Job security is a factor of job satisfaction.				
15-	Pleasant working environment could be reason of job satisfaction.				
16-	Handsome salary is the reason of Job satisfaction.				
17-	Good response from patients may increase job satisfaction.				
18-	Long duty hours result in high risk of getting infection.				
19-	Self-actualization may increase job satisfaction.				
20-	Social acceptance of people may increase job satisfaction.				

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